

Accelerated Collatz Hypothesis: A Mathematical and Intuitive Approach

Abstract

The simplified equations provide a new perspective to the Collatz hypothesis through an accelerated approach. Using an intuitive metaphor, this study demonstrates how the system reaches all positive integers and converges to the ultimate cycle of $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$. This approach bridges mathematical simplicity and intuitive understanding.

Introduction

The Collatz hypothesis posits that starting from any positive integer, repeated application of two rules will eventually lead to the number 1. The problem is formulated as follows:

1. If n is even, $n = n / 2$.
2. If n is odd, $n = 3n + 1$.

This study simplifies the $3n+1$ step to the form $(3n+1)/2$, based on the fact that $3n + 1$ always produces an even number. Combining it with the subsequent division by 2 eliminates unnecessary intermediate steps. Additionally, an intuitive 'machine and balls' metaphor is employed to provide both mathematical and conceptual insight.

Simplified Equations

While the original Collatz hypothesis uses the rules $n/2$ and $3n+1$, the accelerated approach proposed in this paper replaces these with the following simplified rules:

1. If n is even, $n = n / 2$.
2. If n is odd, $n = (3n+1) / 2$.

Analysis of Odd Numbers

In the simplified equation $(3n+1)/2$, odd numbers now yield either odd or even results with equal probability. For better understanding, the equation for odd numbers can be expressed as:

$$n + (n / 2 + 0.5)$$

Here, $n / 2 + 0.5$ represents the growth factor of the odd number n . Let this growth factor be k . Then:

1. If k is odd, the result will be even.
2. If k is even, the result will be odd.

This demonstrates the system's dual nature of chaos and order, with equal probabilities for both outcomes in odd numbers.

Machine and Balls Metaphor

Imagine a machine and a ball:

1. We place the ball into the machine. The machine processes it and gives us 2 balls ($1 \rightarrow 2$).
2. These two balls are fed into the machine, which processes them and returns 1 ball ($2 \rightarrow 1$).
3. The system enters a cycle during this process ($1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$).
4. At this point, the number 3 emerges. One of the two balls is processed, leading to the sequence ($3 \rightarrow 5 \rightarrow 8 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$). At this stage, all numbers are effectively within reach.

This cycle demonstrates that all positive integers are processed and ultimately converge to the cycle $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$.

Exclusion of Zero

The simplified formulation renders zero irrelevant to the hypothesis, as shown below:

1. Starting with $n = 0$, the equation $3 \times 0 + 1 = 1$ leads directly to 1. However, this step does not influence the broader structure of the system.
2. Excluding zero in the simplified formula does not impact the general validity of the hypothesis.

Conclusion and Discussion

The accelerated Collatz hypothesis optimizes the problem, providing both a mathematical and an intuitive solution. The new cycle, $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$, confirms that all positive integers are processed and reach a stable state. This method offers a novel perspective on the Collatz hypothesis, enhancing its efficiency and comprehensibility.

Closing Note

This work reflects the belief in the mathematical nature of reality, even when conceived by individuals who have faced societal exclusion. If this solution is accepted, it may highlight how 'madness' can contribute positively to humanity.